

**EXPRESSION OF PARALINGUISTIC MEANS IN COMMUNICATION
BEHAVIOR. (KINESICS ELEMENT).**

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ANOTATSIYA

Og'zaki bo'lmagan muloqot elementlarini ko'rib chiqish muloqotning madaniyatlararo ma'nosini ifodalash usullarini yaxshiroq tushunishga yordam beradi. Muloqotning og'zaki bo'lmagan elementlariga quyidagilar kiradi: kinesika, taktil xatti-harakatlar, sensorika, proksemikalar, xronemikalar, paralingvistik vositalar. Ushbu maqola faqatgina og'zaki bo'lmagan muloqotning kinesika turinida yoritishga hizmat qiladi.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Изучение элементов невербального общения помогает лучше понять способы выражения межкультурного смысла общения. К невербальным элементам общения относятся: кинесика, тактильное поведение, сенсорика, проксемика, хронемика, паралингвистические средства. Эта статья лишь проливает свет на кинесику невербального общения.

ANNOTATION

Examining the elements of non-verbal communication helps to better understand the ways of expressing the intercultural meaning of communication. Non-verbal elements of communication include: kinesics, tactile behavior, sensorics, proxemics, chronemics, paralinguistic means. This article only serves to shed light on the kinesics of non-verbal communication.

Kinesics is a set of gestures, poses, and body movements used as additional expressive tools in communication. This term was proposed for the study of communication through body movements. Kin is the smallest unit of action, just as speech consists of words, sentences and phrases, behavior also consists of them. Elements of kinesics are gestures, facial expressions, postures and gaze. Gestures are various movements of the body, hands or hands that accompany a person's speech in the process of communication and directly express their attitude to the interlocutor; a nickname, indicating an event, another person, something, a person's wishes and status . Gestures can be arbitrary and involuntary and culturally determined. Many gestures are culturally determined, symbolic and traditional. Every nation and every culture has its own silent film. Once Ch. Chaplin said: "I will tell you where you were

born if I see your movements and gestures." Misinterpretation of a non-verbal message by speakers of one culture by representatives of another culture can lead to unwanted conflicts and dangerous consequences. The following types of gestures are distinguished in intercultural communication:

- 1) the same or very similar gestures have different meanings in different cultures;
- 2) different gestures have the same meaning;
- 3) there may be a coincidence at the level of gestures and meanings, but the designation of these gestures in the languages may be different.

Consider the first type of gestures, for example, the cinema "ring" (OK, ring, zero). The gestural form of the "Ralka" sign has entered Russian culture relatively recently, its main sphere of existence has become the Russian youth environment and business sphere. This gesture is derived from the American kinetic system and means "all is well, all is well." Meanwhile, in Japan, the same form is related to the buying and selling situation. In Venezuela and Brazil, this form of gesture has a clear sexual connotation. There is a famous story told by the American psychologist G. Triandis: once President R. Nixon offended the Brazilians by depicting the "o" button. In Tunisia, the shape looks a little different - except for all the fingers. the index finger and thumb are extended vertically upwards and have a completely different meaning: "I will kill you." In Greece and the Italian island of Sardinia, the form of the gesture is the same as in the United States, and the meaning of the gesture can be roughly described as "push". Kinema "finger to the temple". If a German touches his temple with his finger when talking about someone, it means that the person is "a little crazy". At the same time, in a number of African cultures, a similar form of gesture means a gesture of a person deep in thought. In France, this gesture means that the person being spoken to is stupid, while in Holland, this form means that the person is intelligent. there is a variant of the sign). In Austria, the form "index finger near the lower eyelid" means contempt for the addressee, in Florence "good will" and in Spain - "distrust". In France, the index finger near the lower eyelid is a lying gesture, more precisely, it means: "I am considered a liar", but in Russia it is even a borrowed gesture neither. Consider the second type of gestures. For example, the meaning of "insult". In Spain, "I'm sorry for you" is expressed by touching the earlobe or picking up the earpiece. In Greece, the same meaning is expressed with a raised hand with an open palm facing the recipient. It means "yes". In Bulgaria, when confirming and agreeing, they shake their head from left to right, "Yes" or when clicking, that is, the gesture is always

accompanied by a voice. In Russia, they shake their heads from top to bottom, and the gesture does not necessarily require verbal or other vocal accompaniment, in the strict sense of the word symbol. Bowing is unknown among the Ainu of northern Japan. To express the meaning of "yes", the Ainu use their hands, that is, as a sign of approval and consent, both hands are placed on the chest and move up and down with open palms. The dark-skinned Semang pygmies of central Malaya thrust their chin forward to indicate "yes" and lower their eyes to indicate "no". Arabs want to express the meaning of "yes" by shaking their heads from side to side, and the meaning of "no" is conveyed by shaking their heads and usually by slightly clicking their tongues. Bengalis from Calcutta they quickly shake their head four times in an arc from their shoulders and raise their head and chin to express a Maori non-verbal meaning (interestingly, the Sicilians express "no". Go here). Consider the third type of gestures. For example, Russians and Spanish use "nod" and "shake" in terms of meaning. It is pressed equally with gestures. But there are some inconsistencies at the level of language units where these head movements are recorded. Wednesday: Russian phrases He nodded and He shook his head. In the first case, it is clear that the person agreed, and in the second case, he refused. Well, the Spanish agree and disagree with gestures just like us, but the Spanish equivalent of "nod your head" means "yes." Experts in the field of Spanish language and linguistic culture can explain why this happened. An interesting example is given by V.V. Red: English people can put their fingers on the combination "fig" during a conversation. For the English, such a gesture can be completely semantic: it is just a convenient "pose" of the hand (By the way, the hands can be folded in the same way on the child's stomach). [Krasnih, 2003, p. 324] facial expressions represent all changes in a person's facial expression that can be observed in the process of communication. This is an important element of non-verbal communication. Facial expressions allow you to express all universal emotions: sadness, joy, fear, surprise, anger. However, different forms of manifestation of human emotions often have their own characteristics. In all Western countries, laughter is associated with humor and joy. In Japan, laughter is a sign of embarrassment and insecurity, so misunderstandings often occur when the European is angry and the Japanese partner smiles in embarrassment. Studies in Poland, Hungary, and the United States show that Eastern Europeans prefer to suppress negative emotions and show positive emotions among "themselves," while , among whom it is perfectly appropriate and acceptable to display negative emotions. strangers". Americans express anger, fear or disgust among

"themselves" (relatives and in front of friends) among "strangers" (strangers or strangers) are considered more acceptable. 'they are expressed differently. For example, better than Germans and Americans, pretend to be disgusted, but do not express sadness and anger.

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